

STRATEGIES FOR FORMING THE LEADERSHIP SKILLS OF STUDENTS THROUGH PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract: In this article, scientific-theoretical comments are made about the strategies of using physical education training in the formation of students' leadership abilities.

Key words: Educational system, strategy, leadership ability, physical activity, theoretical skills, position.

Recently, interest in the problem of leadership in society has increased significantly.

Leadership is the art of influencing people, inspiring them to achieve certain goals of their own volition. A leader is a person who unites and directs group actions. Leadership and success are two links in the same chain, and the way to success is through the development of leadership in a person.

It is widely believed that nature has not endowed all people with leadership qualities. But many studies prove that these qualities can be bought. Professor A. D. Novikov, one of the founders of the theory of physical education, formulated an important methodological position that any quality can be cultivated only through activity and in the process of activity. Currently, there are many factors that influence the formation and development of leadership skills and abilities of young people.

In this work, I want to consider the impact of physical education and sports on the development of leadership qualities of our students. A person's ability to become a leader largely depends on the development of his organizational and communicative qualities. According to E. Zharikov and E. Krushelnitsky, a real leader should have the following characteristics: Will, mental stability, criticality, endurance, optimism, determination, flexibility, demanding of himself and others, inclination to new things, persistence, initiative, independence, self-criticism, reliability, stress resistance, ability to change the behavior style.

In the process of physical education, the formation of leadership qualities takes place through the modeling of life situations in which we play through physical exercises, sports, and especially game moments. The most radical means of forming voluntary character traits during training is the load. Physical exercises are considered by us not only as a means of improving technique and tactics, ensuring physical fitness, but also as a means of developing the will. During the learning process, students face certain challenges that help them develop willful character traits. This is the need to master the complex techniques of sports exercises, demonstrate strong-willed actions, overcome fatigue, maintain self-control and performance in adverse environmental conditions, regulate the emotional state, maintain and adhere to a set schedule. All these difficulties are most manifested during sports competitions, which serve as one of the main means of forming a young man's willpower. Naturally, different types of physical exercises and sports educate and shape the mental qualities of young people at different levels.

Doing physical education and sports also affects the development of thinking ability and speed - high demands are placed on the ability to act quickly and adequately in a changing situation and thinking - looking for the reasons for successful and unsuccessful actions, understanding their goals necessity. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account other developing qualities of a person: enthusiasm and goal-seeking. Achieving goals, even the consciousness of approaching them, is the main factor that gives a person satisfaction from his work. In the course of training, this effect is achieved as a result of realizing the progress in mastering the technique of sports exercises, developing motor and mental qualities, and winning competitions.

During training, the student gets to know himself from new, previously unknown sides, confirms himself in his mind. Active motor activity regulates the processes of excitation and inhibition of the central nervous system. Training sessions, participation in sports competitions with high demands on the body can reduce and sometimes completely neutralize negative emotional experiences that appeared earlier. Due to the essence of physical education and sports, the manifestation of negative character traits in them - cowardice, unwillingness, rudeness, negative in behavior - and vice versa, courage, determination, courage are accepted as examples.

Thus, it becomes clear that in the process of physical training and sports, training not only individual physical qualities, but also a number of mental qualities necessary in human life, including leadership and self-discipline, occurs spontaneously and naturally. .

In this work, using various sources, we investigated the relationship between physical education, sports participation and positive mental qualities of a person, including the formation of leadership. Practice shows that our sports graduates feel free and confident in later life, it is easier for them to adapt to new conditions. They will find a suitable place in life, achieve great results at work.

Each person's success is individual and the path to it can be determined only by the person himself. But one thing is certain: success cannot be achieved by being passive, so the only way to achieve success is through leadership.

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